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Enhancing strength and ductility of xanthan gum–stabilized clayey sand: Impact of polypropylene fiber content and length

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ABSTRACT

The use of Xanthan Gum (XG) as a sustainable, eco-friendly biopolymer stabilizer has recently attracted significant interest in geotechnical engineering. Although XG improves soil cohesion and compressive strength, it often leads to brittle stress–strain behavior with a sudden post-peak strength loss, especially in surface-stabilized soils under low confining pressure. This study aims to enhance the brittle behavior of XG-treated clayey sand by adding Polypropylene (PP) fibers. Three XG contents (0.25 %, 0.50 %, and 0.75 %) and two PP fiber lengths (6 and 12 mm) were tested at two dosages (0.4 % and 0.8 %) to explore how fibers of different lengths and contents reinforce the soil. Unconfined compressive strength (UCS) tests were used to evaluate stress–strain behavior, secant modulus (E_{sec}), modulus at 50 % strength (E_{50}), absorbed energy, post-peak stress ratio, and failure patterns. Microstructural analyses with scanning electron microscopy (SEM) were also conducted to examine the reinforcement mechanism and fiber–matrix interaction. Results showed that adding fibers of various lengths and dosages increased compressive strength, absorbed energy, and post-peak stress ratio, while decreasing initial stiffness. At a fixed fiber length, doubling the fiber content significantly increased the UCS; the optimal dosages were 0.8 % for short fibers and 0.4 % for long fibers. SEM images confirmed uniform fiber distribution and strong bonding among fibers, the XG matrix, and soil particles. The combined use of XG and PP fibers offers a practical, sustainable way to improve the ductility of surface-stabilized soils.

1. Introduction

In recent years, population growth and urban expansion have significantly reduced the availability of suitable lands for civil engineering projects. This issue has posed serious challenges for geotechnical engineers, including soil erosion, differential settlements, liquefaction, low bearing capacity, slope instability, and soil swelling and shrinkage. Neglecting these problems can lead to considerable financial losses and even human casualties. Therefore, identifying soil behavior and employing effective methods to enhance its mechanical properties and stability are among the key aspects in the design of geotechnical structures. One of the main approaches to address problematic soils is to alter their inherent properties through soil improvement techniques [1,2]. Soil improvement comprises a set of techniques aimed at enhancing the engineering quality of weak grounds and mitigating geotechnical deficiencies [3].

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Depending on soil type, improvement depth and extent, execution feasibility, environmental considerations, and cost, various methods such as stabilization with additives, reinforcement, densification, and lowering of the groundwater table are employed [4].

Among various methods, soil stabilization using additives is considered one of the most effective and oldest approaches to ground improvement [5]. In this method, soil is mixed with a variety of additives—both traditional and non-traditional—to enhance its mechanical behavior. Traditional stabilizers such as cement, lime, and fly ash have shown acceptable performance in improving soil strength and durability, reducing permeability, and mitigating liquefaction. However, these materials have significant environmental impacts. The emission of greenhouse gases such as CO₂ and NO_x during their production process represents one of the most critical environmental challenges associated with their use [6,7]. In addition, permanent alteration of soil pH, reduced vegetation growth, deterioration of groundwater quality, and the brittle behavior of soil under dynamic loading are other drawbacks of these materials. Consequently, in recent decades, researchers have increasingly sought environmentally friendly alternatives. Recent studies indicate that the substitution of conventional stabilizers with bio-based and sustainable additives can preserve soil strength while minimizing carbon emissions and adverse environmental effects [8].

Among these alternatives, biopolymers, as a new generation of bio-based additives, have attracted increasing attention in geotechnical engineering due to their environmental compatibility, renewability, and ability to form strong bonds among soil particles. Comprehensive recent reviews have shown that biopolymers, through the formation of physical and chemical bonds at the microscale, can effectively enhance interparticle adhesion and soil stability [9,10]. Among various types, polysaccharides such as agar, guar, gellan, and xanthan gums exhibit superior performance in improving cohesion and reducing erosion because of their long-chain molecular structures and diverse ionic charges [11–14]. These materials are derived from natural sources such as algae, fungi, and bacteria, and are characterized by high thermal and chemical stability while being biodegradable and environmentally friendly [15–18]. Therefore, this approach has paved the way for the application of specific bio-based stabilizers such as xanthan gum in recent geotechnical studies [19].

Xanthan gum is one of the most widely used polysaccharide-based biopolymers, first discovered in the 1950s by researchers from the U.S. Regional Research Laboratories through the fermentation of the bacterium *Xanthomonas campestris* [20]. Numerous studies have demonstrated its effectiveness in improving the geotechnical behavior of soils. For instance, the addition of 2 % xanthan gum to kaolin clay increased its liquid limit by 1.32 times [21]; the compressive strength and elastic modulus of high-plasticity clays increased while the swelling pressure decreased by up to 54 % with 1 % xanthan gum [22]; cohesion and internal friction angle of sand improved compared to cement-stabilized samples [23]; and the unconfined compressive strength of Shanghai clay was enhanced by up to 120 % [24]. In addition, xanthan gum has been shown to increase the shear strength of silty clay compared with guar gum [25] and to reduce hydraulic conductivity and permeability by nearly 1000 times with the addition of only 0.25 % xanthan gum [26]. Recent studies have also revealed that xanthan gum exhibits more stable performance than traditional mineral additives in the stabilization of expansive and weak subgrade soils [27]. These findings confirm that xanthan gum can serve as a sustainable and low-carbon substitute for conventional stabilizers while improving soil strength and durability. However, one of the main challenges in xanthan gum-stabilized soils is the occurrence of brittle behavior due to reduced failure strain [22]. This limitation restricts its application in surface soil layers with low confining pressure. To overcome this drawback, the inclusion of randomly distributed fibers has been proposed as a complementary approach to mitigate brittleness by increasing ductility, energy absorption, and residual strength of the stabilized soil [28].

Since ancient times, humans have recognized the concept of soil reinforcement as a means to overcome the mechanical weaknesses of soils by observing the behavior of natural materials in their surroundings [29]. Historical evidence indicates that ancient civilizations such as Babylon, Egypt, and China used natural materials—such as reeds, mats, and plant roots—to increase soil stability and prevent failure [30]. While soil exhibits acceptable resistance under compressive loads, it is inherently weak in tension. Therefore, introducing elements with adequate tensile strength has proven to be an effective method for improving the mechanical behavior of soils. The combination of soil and reinforcing materials results in a composite material known as *reinforced soil*, which possesses both high compressive and tensile strength. The applications of fiber-reinforced soil encompass a wide range of geotechnical engineering practices, including (1) reducing slope failure risk, (2) improving pavement stability, (3) reinforcing foundations and retaining structures, (4) increasing soil tensile strength, (5) constructing embankments, (6) enhancing energy absorption capacity for earthquake-resistant structures, and (7) increasing liquefaction resistance [31–34].

Reinforcing elements within the soil mass can be arranged in specific orientations; however, in recent years, the use of discrete fibers with random distribution has emerged as a new and promising reinforcement technique in geotechnical engineering [35]. These fibers are incorporated into the soil in a manner similar to traditional additives such as cement and lime and are randomly distributed within the soil matrix. The presence of fibers prevents the formation and propagation of weak planes and tensile cracks, thereby enhancing the stability and ductility of the soil structure. Furthermore, the fiber-reinforced soil structure is largely unaffected by environmental conditions such as moisture or temperature variations, resulting in a more stable mechanical response [36–39]. Review studies classify fibers into two main categories: natural fibers (such as coir, jute, and palm fibers) and synthetic fibers (including polyethylene, polyester, steel, glass, polypropylene, and polyvinyl alcohol). Recent investigations have also emphasized the utilization of industrial waste-derived fibers to develop sustainable, high-strength, and low-carbon construction materials [40]. Among various types, polypropylene fibers are widely used in soil improvement due to their high tensile strength, chemical stability in acidic and alkaline environments, corrosion resistance, and hydrophobic nature [41].

In 2023, Ma et al. conducted unconfined compressive strength (UCS) and indirect tensile strength (ITS) tests to investigate the effect of flax fibers on sandy soil stabilized with xanthan gum. The results demonstrated that xanthan gum, by adhering to the surface of soil particles after drying, filling the voids between them, and improving the fiber network, enhanced both compressive and tensile strengths [42]. Chen et al. reported that the addition of fibers reduced the brittleness of silty clay stabilized with xanthan gum [43]. Similarly, Weng et al. found that the strength of red clay stabilized with xanthan gum and reinforced with polypropylene fibers was

approximately 1.9–2.4 times higher than that of xanthan gum–stabilized soil alone, and the fibers significantly improved the ductility of the treated soil [44]. Lv et al. [45] also examined the performance of microbially induced carbonate precipitation (MICP)-stabilized sand reinforced with three different fiber types—polypropylene, basalt, and carbon fibers—at varying contents (0.1–0.8 %) and a fiber length of 12 mm. Their unconfined compressive strength results revealed that polypropylene fibers exhibited greater elongation at failure compared to the other fibers, resulting in higher residual strength and improved energy absorption capacity [45]. Furthermore, Arabani et al. (2025) showed that combining xanthan gum with animal-based fibers enhanced the cyclic durability and ductility of soil under freeze–thaw conditions [46]. Similarly, Mansourkiaei et al. (2025) demonstrated that the inclusion of natural raspberry fibers alongside xanthan gum significantly increased the compressive strength and cyclic durability of bentonite subgrade soil. This study introduced the combination of xanthan gum biopolymer with bio-based organic fibers as a sustainable and effective approach for reinforcing and stabilizing fine-grained subgrade soils [47].

Despite increasing interest in resilient stabilizers in geotechnical engineering, the brittle nature of Xanthan Gum (XG)-stabilized soils remains a challenge under low confining stresses. While prior research demonstrates that XG significantly increases soil compressive strength, it often leads to brittle failure, characterized by a sudden decline in strength after reaching peak strength, especially in surface-stabilized layers. A review of current literature shows that studies on combining Xanthan Gum with Polypropylene (PP) fibers to enhance mechanical properties and reduce soil issues are limited in addressing brittleness. Additionally, there is little clarity on how fiber length and dosage affect the mechanical behavior of biopolymer-stabilized soils. To address this gap, the current study examines how Xanthan Gum and Polypropylene (PP) fibers work together to reduce the brittleness of XG-stabilized clayey sand. Unconfined compressive strength (UCS) tests measured the secant modulus (E_{sec}), the modulus at 50 % strength (E_{50}), the post-peak stress ratio, and energy absorption to assess how fiber reinforcement, with different lengths (short and long) and dosages (low and high), improves the mechanical response of XG-stabilized soils. Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) was employed to examine the microstructural mechanisms and link microscopic features to the overall mechanical behavior. This integrated experimental and microstructural analysis offers new insights into how PP fibers reinforce XG-stabilized soils, a topic that has not been thoroughly studied.

2. Materials and experimental methods

2.1. Soil composition and characterization

This study examines the effects of stabilization and reinforcement on a soil mixture consisting of 20 % clay and 80 % sand, a composition commonly employed in deep mixing columns, dam cores, and pavement layers. Previous studies by Ramachandran et al. [48] and Chang et al. (2015) have demonstrated that xanthan gum-stabilized sand-clay mixtures exhibit superior mechanical behavior compared to pure sand stabilized with xanthan gum. This improvement is primarily due to the filling of sand voids by clay particles and the formation of strong bonds between the clay and biopolymer [15,48]. Moreover, findings by Berkane et al. (2022) suggest that incorporating 20 % clay into XG-stabilized sand (with an XG of 0.25 %) significantly enhances shear strength parameters [49]. Based on these insights, the present study uses this soil composition to evaluate the combined effects of stabilization and fiber reinforcement systematically. This soil type is commonly used in the cores of earth dams, subgrade layers of pavements, and deep mixing columns.

The sand used in this study was sourced from the Caspian Sea coastline, while the clay was obtained from a trench in northern Iran. The grading curve analysis conducted according to ASTM D422 revealed that the sand has a coefficient of uniformity ($C_u = 1.932$), coefficient of curvature ($C_c = 1.102$), and median particle diameter ($D_{50} = 0.214$ mm), classifying it as poorly graded sand (SP) under the Unified Soil Classification System (USCS) [50]. The used clay was also extracted from a trench around Amol. Testing results according to ASTM D4318 determined the Atterberg limits: liquid limit (LL = 52 %), plastic limit (PL = 20 %), and plasticity index (PI = 32 %), classifying it as a high-plasticity clay (CH) [51]. The grading curve is illustrated in Fig. 1.

The specific gravity of the sand and clay particles, measured according to ASTM D854, was 2.78 and 2.68, respectively [52]. Microscopic analysis indicated that Babolsar sand particles exhibit a semi-rounded to sub-angular shape, while the clay particles

Fig. 1. Grain size distribution curve of sand and clay.

exhibit a platy morphology. The relatively high specific gravity of Babolsar sand is attributed to the presence of iron oxide, nickel, and cobalt [53].

2.2. Xanthan gum (XG)

Biopolymers have gained considerable traction in geotechnical engineering due to their environmentally friendly and sustainable properties. XG, an anionic polysaccharide with the chemical formula $C_{35}H_{49}O_{29}$, is produced via aerobic fermentation by the bacterium *Xanthomonas campestris* [54,55]. The molecular structure of XG, depicted in Table 1, consists of repeating glucose, mannose, and glucuronic acid units, enabling it to form electrostatic interactions with soil particles, thereby enhancing soil cohesion and mechanical stability [17,56].

Incorporating XG into soil reduces permeability by filling void spaces within sandy soils, enhancing erosion resistance, and improving overall mechanical strength. Additionally, XG demonstrates excellent resistance across various temperatures and pH levels, making it suitable for diverse environmental conditions [57,58]. In this study, XG was utilized at concentrations of 0.25 %, 0.50 %, and 0.75 %, and its technical specifications are detailed in Table 1.

2.3. Polypropylene fibers (PP Fibers)

PP fibers have gained prominence among synthetic fibers due to their low production cost, high tensile strength, elevated melting point, and exceptional resistance to acidic and alkaline environments [59,60]. UCS tests conducted by Sharma et al. (2015) on clayey sand mixtures with varying fiber contents (0.4 %, 0.8 %, 1.0 %, and 1.1 %) indicated that samples containing 0.8 %, 1.0 %, and 1.1 % fibers demonstrated acceptable mechanical properties [61]. Additionally, Hu et al. (2021) identified an optimal fiber content range between 0.45 % and 0.8 % [62]. Based on these results, fiber contents of 0.4 % and 0.8 % were deliberately selected in this study to represent the lower and upper bounds of the effective range. Two fiber lengths, 6 mm and 12 mm, were utilized to investigate the influence of short versus long fibers in reinforcing XG-stabilized matrices. The physical and mechanical properties of the fibers are presented in Table 2.

2.4. Sample preparation process

Achieving sample homogeneity is a critical aspect of laboratory testing to ensure the accuracy and reliability of experimental results. The recommended compaction rate for embankment soils for construction projects is typically 95 % of the maximum dry density. Accordingly, based on the parameters obtained from compaction tests, the mold volume, and the compaction energy required to achieve 95 % maximum dry density, the weight of dry soil and the required amount of water were calculated. The defined weight

Table 1
Technical properties of XG.

<i>XG shape</i>	<i>XG Chemical structure [17]</i>
<i>Description</i>	<i>Value</i>
Physical state	Powder
Color	White
pH	7.16
Viscosity (1% KCL, cps)	1520

Table 2
Physical and mechanical properties of PP fibers Technical properties of XG.

<i>PP shape</i>	
<i>Description</i>	<i>Value</i>
Fiber type	Discrete
color	white
Unit weight	0.91 g/cm ³
Average diameter	0.034 mm
Length	6-12 mm
Tensile strength	400 MPa
Modulus of elasticity	3500 MPa
Melting point	160 °C
Burning point	590 °C
Reaction with water	Hydrophobic

ratios for XG, ranging from 0.25 % to 0.75 %, and polypropylene fibers, at 0.4 % and 0.8 %, were determined relative to the soil mixture's dry weight, consisting of 80 % sand and 20 % clay.

After establishing the necessary material quantities, the sample preparation began. Sand and clay were thoroughly combined using a mechanical mixer until the mixture was homogeneous. Next, adhering to Chang et al. (2015)'s dry-mixing method, Xanthan Gum powder was first incorporated into the dry soil and mixed until evenly dispersed. Water was then gradually added to attain the desired moisture content [6].

To ensure uniform distribution of fibers within the soil matrix, an essential preparatory step involved separating the fibers using compressed air for 5 min in a controlled chamber before mixing [63]. The pre-separated fibers were then incorporated into the soil, along with the stabilizing agent and water. The moisture in the mixture before fiber addition helped prevent fiber floating and facilitated uniform dispersion [45]. Since manual mixing provides better control over fiber distribution, particularly in small-scale laboratory tests, the fibers were initially separated by hand within the soil before final mixing using a mechanical stirrer [64].

Achieving an even distribution of fibers without clumping is challenging and time-consuming, especially at higher fiber content levels (0.8 %). Although polypropylene fibers can be easily mixed into soil like conventional stabilizers, preparing fiber-reinforced samples requires extensive trial-and-error. The prolonged mixing process and mechanical agitation often result in moisture loss from the soil. Several trial samples were prepared to estimate moisture loss during sample preparation and address this issue. The calculated moisture deficit was then compensated for by adding the appropriate amount of water to the final mixture.

The wet tamping method was employed for sample compaction. The soil was compacted to 95 % of the maximum dry density in a cylindrical mold measuring 102 mm in height and 50 mm in diameter, using a metal rammer in five layers. To ensure proper bonding and continuity between layers, grooves were created at 10 % of each layer's thickness. Special care was taken during this process, particularly for fiber-reinforced samples with 0.8 % fiber content, to prevent fiber breakage. The compacted samples were then extracted from the mold using a hydraulic jack.

The specimens were cured for 7 days under controlled environmental conditions (23 ± 2 °C and 95 ± 5 % RH) within sealed plastic covers to ensure uniform moisture distribution and complete bonding between soil particles and stabilizers. This 7-day curing period was selected based on the findings of Abbasi et al. (2025), which demonstrated that approximately 80–85 % of the maximum compressive strength of XG-stabilized clayey sand was achieved within this timeframe. Therefore, it was identified as the optimal duration for consistent mechanical performance [65]. Following the curing period, the samples were subjected to controlled air drying

at 30 °C in an oven for 24 h, a temperature chosen based on prior research [66,67]. This mild thermal treatment facilitates the gradual removal of free moisture. It promotes the hardening of hydrogel bonds, enabling the development of a stable XG–soil gel network without causing shrinkage cracks or polymer degradation. To validate the results, two specimens were prepared and tested for each mixing design, with the mean error calculated after each test. Results were considered acceptable if the average error was below 5 %. The detailed sample preparation procedure is illustrated in Fig. 2.

2.5. Unconfined compressive strength (UCS) test

The unconfined compressive strength (UCS) test, conducted following ASTM D2166, determines the compressive strength of cylindrical soil specimens under zero confining pressure conditions. The test is performed under strain-controlled conditions, where axial load is applied to the specimen until failure occurs. The termination criterion for the test is either the point of sample failure or the attainment of an axial strain of 15 %, whichever occurs first [68].

Fig. 2. Stages of XG-stabilized and PP fiber-reinforced soil sample preparation.

This simple and cost-effective test provides a reliable means for evaluating the performance of soil stabilizers, offering valuable insights into the effects of fiber length and content on the compressive strength of XG-stabilized soil. Furthermore, the test allows for identifying the failure plane in the weakest section of the sample, enabling a comprehensive assessment of the soil's failure characteristics.

Before testing, the diameter and height of the specimens are precisely measured to ensure accuracy. The sample is positioned centrally within the testing apparatus, aligning it directly beneath the loading platen to maintain uniform load distribution. During testing, an axial load is applied at a constant strain rate of 1.2 % per minute until the specimen reaches failure. The UCS test results are instrumental in understanding the mechanical behavior of the stabilized soil and optimizing the fiber-reinforcement design for geotechnical applications.

2.6. Microstructural analysis via scanning electron microscopy (SEM)

To investigate the microstructural characteristics of the stabilized and fiber-reinforced soil samples, cubic specimens with dimensions of 1 cm × 1 cm were extracted from UCS-tested samples and analyzed via SEM. Each specimen was mounted on an aluminum stub using carbon tape, coated with gold under high vacuum conditions, and examined at magnifications of 50x, 100x, and 200x to assess the distribution and bonding of xanthan gum and fibers [22,69].

3. Results and discussion

3.1. UCS test results

This section presents and discusses the results of the UCS tests. To achieve a comprehensive understanding of the behavior of the tested samples, several key parameters were analyzed, including stress-strain curves, secant modulus (E_{sec}), secant modulus at 50 % of peak strength (E_{50}), Post-peak stress ratio index, absorbed energy, and failure modes.

3.1.1. The effect of PP fiber addition on the compressive strength of XG-stabilized soil

The effect of PP fiber addition on the compressive strength of XG-stabilized soil was thoroughly examined. Fig. 3(a-d) illustrates the stress-strain curves for untreated soil and soil stabilized with XG at concentrations of 0.25 %, 0.5 %, and 0.75 %. The results indicate that, across all XG content levels, the addition of the biopolymer significantly enhances the compressive strength of untreated soil. The most substantial improvement was observed in soil stabilized with 0.25 % XG, which exhibited a 7.5-times increase in strength

Fig. 3. Stress-Strain curves obtained from UCS tests for fiber-reinforced Samples: (a) Soil reinforced with 0.4 % PP fibers of 6 mm length, (b) Soil reinforced with 0.4 % PP fibers of 12 mm length, (c) Soil reinforced with 0.8 % PP fibers of 6 mm length, (d) Soil reinforced with 0.8 % PP fibers of 12 mm length.

compared to untreated soil [65].

Xanthan Gum (XG) is a high-molecular-weight biopolymer that creates a stable and adhesive gel when it contacts water. Its molecular structure includes active functional groups such as carboxylic acid (COOH) and hydroxyl (OH). The negatively charged COO⁻ groups form electrostatic interactions with positively charged ions on clay particle surfaces, while the OH groups establish hydrogen bonds with surface hydroxyls of clay minerals like Si–OH and Al–OH. In clayey-sand soils, XG monomers form cationic and hydrogen bonds with the electrically charged surfaces of clay particles, forming direct chemical connections. Since sand particles are electrically neutral, such direct bonds do not form in the sandy portion. Instead, the biopolymer functions as a physical bridge, forming a continuous gel network that connects sand particles to one another and to nearby clay clusters. This combination of chemical bonds within the clay fraction and physical bridging between sand grains strengthens the soil's interparticle connections, thereby improving structural stability. These interactions cause a notable boost in unconfined compressive strength and overall mechanical performance of the biopolymer-stabilized soil. This microstructural improvement was further confirmed by SEM images (Fig. 4), which clearly show the transition from a loose particle arrangement in untreated soil to a denser, more cohesive matrix in XG-reinforced soil, verifying the formation of polymer bridges and enhanced particle bonding.

Nevertheless, an optimal XG content exists for this soil type. Increasing the XG concentration from 0.25 % to 0.75 % results in a reduced rate of strength enhancement, indicating that 0.25 % XG is the optimal content for this soil. This behavior can be attributed to excessive hydrogel formation, which increases the spacing between soil particles and introduces weak planes within the soil structure. Despite this, soil stabilized with 0.75 % XG still exhibits 5.4 times the strength of untreated soil. Similar findings by Ramachandran et al. [48] demonstrated that doubling the XG content from 0.5 % to 1 % led to a decline in sand-clay soil performance due to the formation of internal voids within the sample [48].

As shown in Fig. 3, the addition of PP fibers of varying lengths and quantities to XG-stabilized soil results in a notable increase in compressive and residual strength. This enhancement can be attributed to several fiber reinforcement mechanisms:

1. **Load Transfer Mechanism:** Dispersed fibers within the soil matrix mimic the function of plant roots, distributing the applied load over a larger soil volume and reducing stress concentration. This mechanism increases soil strength and improves the soil's post-peak behavior [70].
2. **Confinement Effect:** When the soil is subjected to external loading, the fibers deform, with the outer region of the fibers experiencing tensile forces and the inner region undergoing compressive forces. This creates an internal confining pressure that restricts the lateral movement of soil particles. Additionally, fiber interactions in multiple orientations reduce displacement at fiber intersections, forming a stable three-dimensional structure that enhances soil strength [71].
3. **Bridging Effect:** Fibers act as bridges across soil particles and potential failure planes, connecting them during loading and preventing the formation and propagation of microcracks into larger cracks, thereby enhancing the soil's overall structural integrity.
4. **Frictional Resistance:** The interaction between fibers and soil particles generates frictional resistance, limiting particle movement and further improving soil strength [42,72].

In addition to improving peak compressive strength, these mechanisms collectively enhance residual strength. During post-peak deformation, the mobilized fibers continue to transfer tensile forces across developing cracks and resist further particle displacement through interfacial friction. This progressive load transfer mechanism prevents sudden stress drops and maintains a stable residual stress level.

Based on these reinforcement mechanisms, the stress-strain relationship of fiber-reinforced XG-stabilized soil can be considered a function of fiber content and length. In this study, 6 mm and 12 mm fibers were selected to represent short and long fibers, respectively. In contrast

fiber contents of 0.4 % and 0.8 % were chosen to represent low and high fiber content scenarios.

Fig. 3 demonstrates that samples containing 0.25 % XG performed better in combination with fibers in terms of both compressive strength and residual strength. Consequently, this study focuses on the effect of fiber length and content on the mechanical behavior of

Fig. 4. SEM images showing the microstructural difference between (a) untreated soil and (b) soil stabilized with 0.25 % XG.

samples stabilized with 0.25 % XG.

3.1.2. Effect of PP fiber content on the compressive strength of XG-stabilized soil

Fig. 5 illustrates the variations in compressive strength and the UCS improvement ratio of fiber-reinforced soil samples, expressed as the ratio of the UCS of soil stabilized with 0.4 % and 0.8 % fibers to that of soil stabilized with 0.25 % XG for fiber lengths of 6 mm and 12 mm. The data varies depending on the used fiber content, specifically for reinforced soil with 6 mm and 12 mm fiber lengths.

In soil stabilized with 0.25 % XG, the role of fibers in enhancing the mechanical properties becomes more pronounced. A detailed analysis of the stress-strain curves reveals that, at a constant fiber length, increasing the fiber content from 0.4 % to 0.8 % improves compressive strength for samples containing XG. Furthermore, as observed in Fig. 3, samples containing 0.8 % fibers retain higher residual stresses, and failure occurs at higher strain levels.

According to Fig. 5, an increase in fiber content in samples reinforced with 12 mm fibers results in an improvement ratio increase from 1.53 to 1.64. However, the highest improvement ratio is observed in samples reinforced with 6 mm PP fibers at a content of 0.8 %, achieving a maximum improvement ratio of 2.11. Therefore, adding 0.8 % fibers, regardless of fiber length, has a more significant positive effect on the compressive strength of stabilized soil.

Fig. 5. Variations in UCS and strength improvement ratio as a function of fiber content for reinforced samples with fiber lengths of 6 mm and 12 mm.

At higher fiber contents (0.8 %), the effective contact surface between soil particles increases compared to samples with lower fiber content (0.4 %), leading to enhanced interfacial forces at the soil-fiber interface. This forms a more robust three-dimensional structure that significantly contributes to the mechanical performance of fiber-reinforced soil. The improved fiber-soil interaction enhances the load transfer mechanism and increases the overall performance of the stabilized soil.

A similar conclusion was reported by Estabragh et al. (2017), who investigated the effects of PP fibers in clay soils, and Yilmaz (2015), who studied the effect of PP on fly ash-stabilized clay [73,74]. Their findings corroborate the observed enhancement in soil

Fig. 6. Variations in UCS and strength improvement ratio as a function of fiber Length for samples reinforced with 0.4 % and 0.8 % fibers.

strength with increasing fiber content, further affirming the effectiveness of PP fibers in soil stabilization applications.

3.1.3. Effect of PP fiber length on the UCS of XG-stabilized soil

As shown in Fig. 6, the effect of fiber length on the compressive strength of XG-stabilized soil is more pronounced in samples with lower fiber contents. In these samples, 12 mm fibers significantly impact compressive strength more than 6 mm fibers. For instance, samples containing 0.4 % of 6 mm fibers achieve an improvement ratio of 1.46, which increases to 1.53 when the fiber length is extended to 12 mm. Conversely, in samples with 0.8 % fiber content, the improvement ratio for 6 mm fibers reaches 2.11, while an increase in fiber length to 12 mm reduces to 1.64.

The number of soil particles in contact with the fibers directly depends on fiber length in a soil-fiber mixture. As the fiber length increases, the contact surface area between soil particles and fibers expands, facilitating more effective interaction and load transfer. This phenomenon is illustrated in Fig. 7-a, where stress distribution across a broader area with longer fibers can be observed. Additionally, longer fibers exhibit greater bending curvature than shorter fibers, leading to a more stable spatial structure within the soil matrix. Consequently, longer fibers provide more effective reinforcement through bending and load transfer mechanisms at lower fiber dosages.

In contrast, the frictional component of the 6 mm fibers may not be fully mobilized due to their shorter length, resulting in lower resistance compared to 12 mm fibers. Thus, when fiber content is low, 12 mm fibers demonstrate superior performance in enhancing soil behavior. Similar findings were reported by Chen et al. (2015), affirming the effectiveness of longer fibers at lower dosages [75].

However, when fiber content increases to 0.8 %, the potential for fiber entanglement becomes more significant. As a result, uneven fiber distribution and the formation of fiber flocs, as shown in Fig. 7-b, are likely to occur during mixing and sample preparation. This issue can reduce the effective contact surface between soil particles, creating weak structural planes and decreasing soil resistance to applied forces. Therefore, longer fibers may exhibit reduced effectiveness at higher fiber contents compared to shorter fibers. A similar observation was made by Boz et al. (2018), who examined the effects of PP fibers on clay soils and reported a decline in performance with increasing fiber length at higher dosages [76].

In a soil mass with a constant fiber content, the number of shorter fibers is higher than longer fibers, leading to increased inter-particle friction. Additionally, shorter fibers are more likely to pass through slip planes and exhibit a lower tendency for entanglement compared to 12 mm fibers. These factors explain the superior compressive strength observed in soil samples containing 0.8 % of 6 mm fibers. As a result, selecting an appropriate fiber length plays a critical role in optimizing soil performance.

As illustrated in Fig. 8, the highest UCS is achieved when the XG content is 0.25 % and the fiber content is 0.8 % for both 6 mm and 12 mm fiber lengths. This result highlights the optimal combination of stabilizer and fiber content, ensuring improved soil strength and deformation resistance.

3.1.4. Combined effect of biopolymer and fibers on soil

XG plays a crucial role in soil stabilization by coating sand particles and filling voids, acting as a strong bridge that binds the particles together. Additionally, XG forms cationic and hydrogen bonds with clay particles, significantly enhancing the peak strength of the soil. However, the combined effect of XG and PP fibers is particularly remarkable in improving clayey sand soil's peak and residual strength.

As depicted in Fig. 9, the surface of PP fibers is distinctly coated with XG, which facilitates the formation of a strong bond between the fibers and the soil matrix. The biopolymer films create robust interparticle connections, enhancing the interaction between the fibers and the surrounding soil. The PP fibers are randomly distributed throughout the soil and interconnect with each other, forming an integrated reinforcement system. When one fiber undergoes tensile stress, the interconnected fibers are also influenced, forming a three-dimensional stress network. This interconnected network effectively restricts fiber slippage, allowing the fibers to withstand

Fig. 7. a) Effective length of 12 mm fibers and their performance in load transfer, b) Entanglement of 12 mm PP Fibers in XG-stabilized soil.

Fig. 8. Maximum compressive strength in stabilized and reinforced samples with different biopolymer and fiber content levels: a) 6 mm fibers, b) 12 mm fibers.

Fig. 9. Coating of PP Fiber Surface with XG Gum.

higher applied loads. Consequently, soil deformation is significantly reduced, preventing crack propagation and brittle failure while enhancing the overall cohesion and stability of the soil matrix.

The synergistic combination of XG and PP fibers improves the ductility and load-bearing capacity of the stabilized soil. The XG coating ensures uniform load distribution, while the fibers reinforce the soil against tensile stresses, resulting in a well-integrated, durable soil structure that resists external forces more effectively. The recent research by Zhuang and Wang (2025) demonstrates that integrating xanthan gum with natural coconut fiber significantly enhances the compressive strength and ductility of soil through synergistic interactions at both micro- and macrostructural levels. Scanning Electron Microscope (SEM) analysis reveals that xanthan gum forms a gel-like matrix that coats soil particles and facilitates bonding to the rough surfaces of coconut fibers via hydrogen bonds and electrostatic interactions, thereby establishing a stable three-dimensional network within the soil matrix. This biopolymer–fiber composite reduces pore volume and restricts crack propagation, ultimately increasing the residual strength of the specimen post-failure [77]. Similarly, Feng et al. (2023) reported that combining xanthan gum with natural jute fibers markedly improves the compressive and tensile properties of dredged soils. In this context, xanthan gum forms a gel-like matrix around soil particles, while woven jute fibers enhance ductility, cohesion, and crack resistance. These findings support the hypothesis that the synergistic use of biopolymers and natural fibers, regardless of fiber type, offers an effective and sustainable strategy for enhancing the mechanical performance of soils [78].

3.2. Deformation parameters

This section discusses the deformation parameters derived from the UCS tests, explicitly focusing on the secant modulus and the deformation corresponding to 50 % of peak strength.

3.2.1. Secant modulus (E_{Sec})

The secant modulus is defined as the slope of a straight line connecting the origin of the stress–strain curve to a specified strain point. This parameter directly depends on the displacement occurring during loading and reflects the stiffness of the soil–binder–fiber composite system. The variations in the secant modulus can be analyzed at low and high strain levels, each representing distinct deformation mechanisms (i.e., at a strain level of 7×10^{-3} , marking the transition from low to high strain).

1. At low strain levels: The interlocking between soil particles prevents relative sliding, and the deformation mainly arises from the elastic distortion of individual particles. This deformation is reversible, and the reduction in stiffness is negligible.
2. At high strain levels: The deformation mechanism gradually shifts toward interparticle slippage, which is irreversible and results in a noticeable decrease in the secant modulus.

Fig. 10 illustrates the variation of the secant modulus as a function of axial strain in XG-stabilized soil samples reinforced with polypropylene (PP) fibers at various contents and lengths. The analysis of the stress–strain behavior indicates that the incorporation of PP fibers at all tested dosages and lengths results in a marginal decrease in the secant modulus at low strains. This phenomenon can be attributed to the interaction between the xanthan gum matrix and the fibers. At initial strain levels, the specimen’s stiffness is predominantly governed by the hydrogel network formed by xanthan gum, with fibers remaining largely unengaged. The physical presence of fibers may locally disrupt the continuity of the biopolymer matrix, generating slight discontinuities that marginally weaken the stress transfer pathway and consequently reduce the initial slope of the stress–strain curve.

The secant modulus of fiber-reinforced samples remains almost unchanged at low strain levels. The curves show gentler slopes and longer quasi-linear segments, indicating improved soil–fiber interlocking and a delayed occurrence of interfacial slippage. This behavior implies a broader elastic-like deformation range and a gradual activation of interfacial shear resistance between the soil and fibers.

As the strain increases, the relative displacement between soil particles and polypropylene (PP) fibers becomes increasingly

Fig. 10. Variations in secant modulus (E_{Sec}) with axial strain for different stabilized samples: a) Stabilized samples containing 0.4 % PP fibers of 12 mm length, b) Stabilized samples containing 0.4 % PP fibers of 6 mm length, c) Stabilized samples containing 0.8 % PP fibers of 12 mm length, d) Stabilized samples containing 0.8 % PP fibers of 6 mm length.

significant, which activates interfacial shear transfer and mobilizes the fiber resistance. Consequently, the secant modulus during this stage increases relative to unreinforced samples. However, at higher strains, the progressive degradation of xanthan gum bonds results in a secondary decrease in the secant modulus, as the biopolymer bonding network begins to rupture, leading to an increase in effective porosity. Similar observations have been reported by Soleimani and Janalizadeh. [79].

It should be noted that incorporating fibers into soil stabilized with 0.25 % xanthan gum enhances interparticle bonding and particle interlocking, resulting in a secant modulus exceeding that of samples with 0.5 % and 0.75 % xanthan gum. This indicates that, at an optimal xanthan gum concentration, the synergistic effects of biopolymer adhesion and fiber interlocking yield the maximum effective stiffness in the stabilized soil.

3.2.2. Modulus at 50 % of peak strength (E_{50})

The modulus at 50 % of peak strength, a critical indicator for assessing the performance of the biopolymer in the soil, is determined from the slope of the line connecting the origin to the stress value at 50 % of the peak strength on the stress-strain curve. The stiffness of the untreated soil is measured at 2.86 MPa. As shown in Fig. 11, among various XG contents, the addition of 0.25 % XG results in a 32.8-fold increase in soil stiffness, reaching 73.76 MPa. However, as the XG content increases from 0.25 % to 0.75 %, the rate of stiffness improvement declines, with an increase of only 14.47 times for 0.75 % XG. This trend can be attributed to the excessive polymer content, which induces internal pressure among soil particles, leading to particle separation and a subsequent reduction in soil matrix stiffness.

Adding PP fibers to stabilized soil is expected to enhance stiffness by providing confining pressure and preventing the opening of cracks. However, as presented in Fig. 11, a reduction in stiffness is observed with the inclusion of fibers. The following factors can explain this phenomenon:

1. **Initial Deformation Requirement:** PP fibers require a certain degree of initial deformation to become fully mobilized. To reach this threshold stress, many XG bonds within the soil matrix break, reducing overall soil stiffness. Similar observations were reported by Consoli et al. (2009), who studied the effect of PP fiber reinforcement in cement-stabilized sand, and by Janalizadeh Choobasti and Soleimani Kutanaei, who examined the influence of polyvinyl fibers on the deformation characteristics of cemented sand [80, 81].
2. **Reduced Brittleness:** Previous research by Hamidi and Hoeresfand [82] and Tang et al. [83] attributed the reduction in stiffness of fiber-reinforced soil to decreased brittleness. The fibers introduce flexibility into the soil matrix, mitigating the brittle nature of XG-stabilized soil and enabling more significant deformation under applied loads [82,83].

Considering these findings and the aforementioned explanations, the observed decrease in stiffness with fiber addition can be attributed to the increased flexibility of the soil and the disruption of hydrogel bonds within the XG matrix as fibers mobilize. Notably, the fiber-reinforced soil stabilized with 0.25 % XG exhibits the highest stiffness compared to samples containing 0.5 % and 0.75 % XG, highlighting the importance of optimal biopolymer content in achieving improved mechanical performance.

The reduction in the stiffness of fiber-reinforced soil varies depending on the fiber content and length. Since the stiffness of the reinforced samples is influenced by 50 % of peak stress and the corresponding strain at failure—having a direct relationship with the former and an inverse relationship with the latter—a comparative analysis of the strain at failure in reinforced samples is essential to justify the observed stiffness variations.

Fig. 12 illustrates the variations in strain corresponding to failure stress as a function of fiber length. This analysis helps understand

Fig. 11. Modulus at 50 % of peak strength (E_{50}) for XG-stabilized and PP fiber-reinforced Samples.

Fig. 12. Variations of axial Index (AI) with fiber length for XG-stabilized and PP fiber-reinforced samples.

how different fiber lengths affect the strain capacity of the stabilized soil, ultimately impacting its overall stiffness and deformation behavior.

The Axial Index (AI), which quantifies the strain response of the reinforced samples, is calculated using Eq. (1) [84]. This Index provides a comprehensive measure of the influence of fiber inclusion on the deformation characteristics of XG-stabilized soil, facilitating a better understanding of the interaction between fibers and the soil matrix.

$$AI = \Delta_{fiber} / \Delta_{no\ fiber} \tag{1}$$

In the above Equation, AI represents the Axial Index, Δ_{fiber} denotes the strain corresponding to failure stress in the fiber-reinforced

Fig. 13. Effect of fiber length and content on the brittle Index of reinforced samples.

sample, while $\Delta_{no\ fiber}$ Represents the strain corresponding to failure stress in the unreinforced sample.

In fiber-reinforced samples containing 0.25 % XG at a constant fiber length, an increase in fiber content leads to a more pronounced reduction in stiffness. Specifically, adding 0.4 % fibers of 12 mm length results in a 6.23 % reduction in the stiffness of stabilized soil, whereas doubling the fiber content to 0.8 % leads to a 52.75 % reduction in stiffness. As shown in Fig. 13, doubling the fiber content from 0.4 % to 0.8 % at a fiber length of 6 mm results in an approximately 246 % increase in the Axial Index (AI), indicating that fibers become more mobilized at higher strain levels, leading to the breakdown of many hydrogel bonds within the xanthan gum matrix and consequently reducing soil stiffness.

At a constant fiber content, 12 mm fibers exhibit greater stiffness than 6 mm fibers, while the axial Index demonstrates an inverse relationship. For example, when the fiber length is reduced by half in soil stabilized with 0.25 % xanthan gum and 0.8 % PP fibers, the soil stiffness decreases by 15.1 %.

These findings indicate that the reduction in stiffness of reinforced samples is mainly dependent on the strain corresponding to failure stress, whereas both fiber content and length influence the axial Index. The balance between fiber length and content is crucial in optimizing the mechanical properties of XG-stabilized soils, with longer fibers providing better reinforcement at lower fiber contents. In comparison, shorter fibers distribute more evenly and effectively at higher fiber dosages.

3.2.3. Post-peak stress ratio index

Sudden failure of materials following minimal deformation is indicative of their brittle behavior. However, if the material transitions from brittle to ductile behavior, it will experience significant deformation before failure, acting as an early warning sign. Various methods exist to evaluate the ductility of materials, with the Post-Peak Stress Ratio Index (R_{ps}) being one of the most effective. Eq. (2) defines this Index as directly related to residual strength and inversely to peak stress. Consequently, increased residual stress leads to a higher post-peak stress ratio index, indicating more ductile behavior. In other words, as the R_{ps} Index approaches 100 %, the sample exhibits more excellent ductility [85]:

$$R_{ps} = \frac{q_{res}}{q_u} \times 100 \quad (2)$$

The above Equation R_{ps} represents the post-peak stress ratio index, q_{res} denoting the residual unconfined compressive strength and q_u the peak UCS. The post-peak stress ratio index for unstabilized soil is measured at 77.41 %. As shown in Fig. 13, the addition of XG to the soil, in concentrations ranging from 0.25 % to 0.75 %, results in a decrease R_{ps} , indicating an increase in the brittle behavior of the soil.

One of the key effects of fiber addition to soil is the enhancement of post-peak behavior, which reduces the difference between residual and peak stress values. PP fibers create a strong interparticle connection in the soil matrix. Deformation under tensile strain is controlled by the friction between soil particles and fibers, as well as the tensile strength of the fibers, which leads to an increase in peak stress. Moreover, fibers stretch upon crack formation, bridging the cracks and enhancing the residual strength of the soil. The incorporation of PP fibers in unstabilized soil results in a more ductile behavior and an increase in the post-peak stress ratio index, a trend also reported by Liu et al. (2019) in PP-reinforced sand and Boz et al. (2018) in clayey soils [76,86].

The increase in ductility is a function of both fiber length and content. The results indicate that the brittleness of samples reinforced with 0.8 % fiber content in both 6 mm and 12 mm fiber lengths is significantly reduced. In other words, samples containing 0.8 % fibers exhibit more flexible behavior than others, increasing the post-peak stress ratio index. This increased ductility is attributed to more fibers crossing the failure plane, which establishes stronger connections between cracks and minimizes the loss of strength after peak stress.

As illustrated in Fig. 14, SEM images confirm that a higher fiber content results in a larger surface contact area with the soil, effectively reducing the loss of strength. Similar findings were reported by Malidarreh et al. (2018), who observed improved ductility in fiber-reinforced sandy soil with increased PP content [87].

Fig. 14. SEM images of reinforced samples containing: a) 0.4 % PP fibers of 6 mm length, b) 0.8 % PP fibers of 6 mm length.

Furthermore, based on the results of the UCS tests, it is evident that longer fibers at a 0.4 % concentration provide greater anchoring force, which reduces fiber slippage and enhances soil stability. However, 6 mm fibers lack anchoring due to their shorter length, resulting in weaker soil-fiber interaction. Longer fibers exhibit excellent resistance to pullout during crack formation, preventing a significant reduction in strength and leading to more ductile behavior, corresponding to a higher post-peak stress ratio index (Fig. 15). On the other hand, increasing fiber content in the soil improves the performance of 6 mm fibers in enhancing ductility, leading to a higher post-peak stress ratio index. However, when fiber length is increased to 12 mm, non-uniform distribution and a higher tendency for entanglement reduce the overall ductility compared to shorter fibers.

3.2.4. Absorbed energy

Absorbed energy is a crucial property of materials, particularly in seismic design, as it quantifies the energy required to induce deformation in samples. It is the area under the stress-strain curve up to a specific strain level. Since all fiber-reinforced samples were tested up to 15 % axial strain, the absorbed energy was calculated accordingly.

In stabilized samples, failure strain occurs more rapidly compared to reinforced samples. The stress-strain curve area depends on peak, residual stress, and failure strain. As shown in Fig. 16, adding XG to the soil matrix creates strong interparticle bonds, increasing peak and residual stress values. Consequently, stabilized soil absorbs more energy compared to unstabilized soil. However, as the XG content increases, the absorbed energy increment diminishes. This reduction is attributed to the formation of additional hydrogel structures, which increase the distance between soil particles and reduce peak stress.

The significant impact of fibers on soil stress-strain behavior is primarily seen in the increase in compressive strength, especially residual strength, and strain at failure. The incorporation of fibers shifts the stress-strain curve upward and to the right, increasing the area under the curve and, consequently, the absorbed energy. As illustrated in Fig. 17, adding fibers in all concentrations and lengths enhances the absorbed energy of XG-stabilized soil. However, the most pronounced effect is observed in soil samples stabilized with 0.25 % XG, further analyzed by varying fiber content and length.

The analysis of fiber content effects in Fig. 18 demonstrates that increased PP content results in higher absorbed energy. The improvement ratio (IR) of absorbed energy is defined by Eq. (3):

$$IR = \frac{AE_{XG+PP}}{AE_{XG}} \times 100 \quad (3)$$

The above equation represents the absorbed energy improvement ratio (IR), where AE_{XG+PP} denotes the absorbed energy of the soil stabilized with xanthan gum (XG) and reinforced with polypropylene (PP) fibers, and AE_{XG} refers to the absorbed energy of the reference soil stabilized with 0.25 % XG without fibers. This ratio quantifies the percentage increase in absorbed energy resulting from fiber inclusion in the XG-stabilized soil matrix.

According to Abbasi et al. (2025), the absorbed energy of the soil stabilized with 0.25 % xanthan gum without fibers was 267.80, which is considered here as the baseline value for calculating the improvement ratios [65].

In this study, the improved absorbed energy for samples reinforced with 0.4 % fibers of 6 mm and 12 mm lengths compared to the soil stabilized with 0.25 % XG is 3.38 and 3.71, respectively. Increasing the fiber content to 0.8 % improves ratios of 9.23 for 6 mm fibers and 6.24 for 12 mm fibers. The increase in fiber content enhances factors such as the effective contact surface between soil particles, the number of fibers passing through a given volume, and the probability of fibers bridging failure planes, improving crack resistance and increasing absorbed energy. Since failure strain remains constant and peak stress exhibits minimal changes, residual stress is the dominant factor influencing absorbed energy in this context. Qu and Zhu (2021) reported similar findings, indicating that increasing the content and length of palm fibers enhances peak strength and strain at failure, shifting the failure mode from brittle to ductile and consequently improving energy absorption [88].

Fig. 19 illustrates that longer PP fibers absorb more energy in samples with lower fiber content than shorter fibers. After the

Fig. 15. a) Adequate anchorage length in 12 mm fibers, (b) inadequate anchorage length in 6 mm fibers.

Fig. 16. Absorbed energy variations with XG content in the soil.

Fig. 17. Absorbed energy variation with axial strain for samples reinforced with 0.4 % and 0.8 % fibers of 6 mm and 12 mm lengths.

Fig. 18. Absorbed energy and improvement ratio variations with fiber content for samples reinforced with 6 mm and 12 mm fibers.

Fig. 19. Absorbed energy and improvement ratio variations with fiber length for samples reinforced with 0.4 % and 0.8 % Fibers.

formation of microcracks, longer fibers act as bridges across the cracks, preventing their propagation and delaying failure. The force transfer mechanism through fibers increases the energy absorption capacity, as reflected in the larger stress-strain curve area. However, adding 0.8 % fibers of 12 mm length to stabilized soil can lead to fiber entanglement within the sample, reducing UCS and consequently decreasing energy absorbed.

The improvement ratio of absorbed energy for 0.4 % fiber content increases from 3.38 to 3.71 with increasing fiber length, whereas for 0.8 % fiber content, the improvement ratio decreases from 9.23 to 6.24 with increasing fiber length.

3.3. Failure modes of stabilized and fiber-reinforced samples

The failure modes of samples stabilized with Xanthan Gum and reinforced with Polypropylene fibers were examined during unconfined compressive strength tests. Notably, fiber-reinforced samples exhibited failure patterns that differed significantly from those observed in samples stabilized only with Xanthan Gum. As shown in the schematic diagram of Fig. 20, a clear distinction exists between brittle and ductile failure modes. Failure modes A, B, and C indicate brittle behavior, mainly observed in samples without fibers. Conversely, mode D represents the transition from brittle to ductile failure. Modes E, F, and G demonstrate fully ductile responses, highlighting the influence of fiber reinforcement on failure characteristics [89]. According to Fig. 21, the failure modes (a–c) of the XG-stabilized specimens show distinct variations in failure mechanisms. Specifically, the unreinforced samples exhibited vertical crack propagation throughout the full height of the specimens, leading to brittle, sudden failure with no prior warning signs. This behavior indicates that, in the absence of fibers, stress concentration along vertical planes is the dominant failure mechanism, culminating in an abrupt loss of compressive strength.

The incorporation of 0.4 % and 0.8 % polypropylene (PP) fibers to samples containing 0.25 % xanthan gum (XG) (corresponding to modes d–g) caused notable changes in failure behavior. Reinforced specimens mainly showed barrel-shaped failure, marked by mid-section expansion, increased width at the top, reduced diameter at the bottom, and the development of multiple surface cracks. These failure types—classified as E, F, and G—demonstrate improved ductility due to fiber reinforcement in the soil. Failure was indicated by lateral expansion and the formation of narrow surface cracks. The randomly dispersed polypropylene fibers acted as a lateral restraint within the soil matrix, thereby slowing crack growth, allowing for more gradual deformation, and preventing sudden failure. Notably, samples with 0.8 % fiber content exhibited a more pronounced barrel-shaped failure mode than those with 0.4 % fiber content. The higher fiber concentration enhanced confinement, resulting in increased residual strength and fewer visible cracks. These failure patterns indicate improved energy absorption, higher residual strength, and increased ductility in the 0.8 % fiber-reinforced samples. As a result, adding polypropylene fibers effectively transforms the soil from a failure-prone material into a more stable and ductile system with better post-peak behavior.

4. Conclusion

This study investigates the synergistic effects of xanthan gum (XG) stabilization and polypropylene (PP) fiber reinforcement on the mechanical behavior of clayey sand. A comprehensive experimental program, including unconfined compressive strength (UCS) tests and microstructural analyses, was conducted to evaluate the influence of fiber length (6 mm and 12 mm) and dosage (0.4 % and 0.8 %) on significant parameters such as strength, ductility, stiffness, and energy absorption capacity of XG-stabilized soils. The principal findings are summarized as follows:

1. Adding 0.25 % XG significantly improved the UCS of clayey sand but induced brittle failure due to a 78 % reduction in residual stress ratio. The inclusion of PP fibers mitigated this brittleness, with the best ductility observed in samples containing 0.8 % of 6 mm fibers.
2. The addition of PP fibers enhanced UCS, residual stress, and strain at failure for all combinations of fiber length and dosage. However, the rate of improvement was dependent on the fiber geometry. At a fiber length of 12 mm, increasing the fiber content from 0.4 % to 0.8 % raised the UCS improvement ratio from 1.53 to 1.64.
3. Increasing fiber length improved UCS at the lower dosage (0.4 %), whereas at 0.8 %, shorter fibers (6 mm) produced higher strength. This indicates that the optimal fiber length depends on fiber dosage.
4. Fiber inclusion altered the stiffness behavior of the stabilized soil, reducing both the secant and deformation modulus (at 50 % peak strength) and demonstrating the role of fibers in controlling soil flexibility.
5. Incorporating 0.8 % of 6 mm PP fibers increased the absorbed energy to 1150.85 kJ/m^3 —about 4.3 times higher than the XG-only soil—indicating improved post-peak toughness and better energy dissipation under dynamic loading conditions.
6. SEM analysis confirmed the complementary functions of XG and PP fibers. XG filled voids and bonded soil particles, while PP fibers formed a three-dimensional reinforcement network that limited deformation and enhanced matrix integrity.

The combined use of xanthan gum (XG) and polypropylene (PP) fibers has been demonstrated to substantially improve the compressive strength, ductility, and energy absorption capacity of clayey sand. Furthermore, this synergistic effect reduces the material's brittleness under low confining stress conditions. These results highlight the potential of XG–PP composite systems for

Fig. 20. Schematic representation of brittle vs. ductile failure modes [83].

Fig. 21. Failure modes of XG-stabilized and PP fiber-reinforced samples.

stabilizing near-surface soil layers, pavement subgrades, and embankments. Future research should investigate the integration of this bio-based stabilization method with microbial-induced calcite precipitation (MICP), nanomaterials, and data-driven optimization techniques to promote the development of sustainable, innovative, and low-carbon geotechnical materials.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Fatemeh Abbasi: Writing – original draft, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation. **Kaveh Roushan:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Supervision, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Conceptualization. **Asskar Janalizadeh Choobasti:** Writing – review & editing, Visualization, Validation, Supervision, Project administration, Formal analysis, Conceptualization.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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